

Article Type

Research Article

Research on the Service Innovation Mechanism of KIBS Enterprise Symbiotic Network

Arrived Date
02.08.2020

Accepted Date
08.08.2020

Published Date
31.10.2020

Wang Boning¹, Wang Ying²

ABSTRACT

With the rapid development of knowledge globalization and service specialization, it is difficult for knowledge intensive business service (hereinafter referred to as the "KIBS enterprises") to maintain original advantages in the fierce competition in the market only through own service innovation in the situation of constant acceleration of knowledge accumulation, service innovation evolution and constant increase of cost. At this time, it will be very necessary for KIBS enterprises to establish a symbiotic model through service innovation cooperation with other organizations, and build KIBS enterprise symbiotic network for collaborative innovation. In this paper, the author starts from the perspective of symbiosis, defines the concept and composition of symbiosis network of KIBS enterprises, proposes the main characteristics of symbiosis network of KIBS enterprises, analyzes the influence of symbiosis network of KIBS enterprises on the service innovation capacity, and summarizes three examples of service innovation of symbiosis network of KIBS enterprises, so as to analyze service innovation mechanism of symbiosis network of KIBS enterprises.

Introduction

With the advent of the knowledge economy era, knowledge-intensive business services (KIBS), characterized by high technology content, high added value of services and high human capital, play an obvious role in optimizing industrial structure, promoting economic development and knowledge service innovation. US Department of Commerce believes that KIBS are service firms that input knowledge products as other business values, or science and technology-related industries that carry out innovation activities while providing services ^[1]. Strambach believes that the essence of KIBS is to acquire, integrate and disseminate knowledge. ^[2]. Tether et al. found that 40% firms in the service industry are conducting service innovation, that 58% firms in the information technology intensive financial services are conducting service innovation, and that 68% firms in the telecommunication service industry are conducting service innovation ^[3]. Service innovation has become an important driving force for the sustainable development of all industries. Therefore, study on KIBS firms' service innovation mechanism has become an important way for improving the service quality and capacity of KIBS firms.

With the rapid development of knowledge globalization, the R&D, diffusion, transfer and dissemination of technology and services have also been accelerated. The life cycle of service products with high technical content is shortened, and the development cost is rising. The risk of service innovation is also increasing. Therefore, it has been more difficult for KIBS firms to generate high revenue through service innovation. From this moment, KIBS firms should change the traditional service innovation mode from independent service innovation to collaborative service innovation. In this context, KIBS firms' development is further integrated into the complicated and dynamic symbiosis network, and is operated as a core unit. And then, the service innovation also takes on the characteristics of a symbiont gradually. Therefore, it is very necessary to introduce the theory of symbiosis to the study on the service innovation and development of KIBS firms. Proposed in the late 19th century, it was firstly applied to study the symbiosis of mutually-dependent and co-developed

organisms, and then, was gradually applied in the sociology, management and economics. It is also applicable to the service innovation and development of KIBS firms. By taking KIBS firms as the core unit of the symbiosis network, this paper defines the concept and composition of symbiosis network of KIBS firms, analyzes the impact of symbiosis network of KIBS firms on service innovation capability, summarizes and puts forward three patterns of symbiosis network of KIBS firms' service innovation points, and then puts forward the service innovation mechanism of symbiosis network of KIBS firms.

Concept of symbiosis network of KIBS firms

Early studies on the firm symbiosis network emphasized in the cooperation relationship between firms, between firms and other organizations, and between firms and other acting subjects which can facilitate its innovation activities. Freeman believes that firm symbiosis network is an interpenetrative organizational form with loose coupling between the market and firms for the purpose of innovation. He also emphasizes that the symbiotic relationship is the foundation of realizing collaborative innovation among symbiotic units in a symbiosis network ^[4]. Lambert believes that a firm symbiosis network refers to that a symbiosis network is established among firms if they share resources, exchange energies or exchange and reuse wastes intensively ^[5]. Mirata believes that a symbiosis network is a long-term symbiotic relationship among firms for the share, circulation and exchanges of materials, energies, information, human resources and technologies. It aims at creating competitive advantage for firms ^[6]. Yuan Zengwei believes that a symbiosis network is an economic network organization for maximizing the economic, environmental and social benefits of firms through material flow connection, value chain linkage, information flow transmission, effective capital operation and cooperation in talent and technology among firms under knowledge and economy conditions, limitation of environmental conditions as well as coordination and guidance of the government ^[7]. Du Pu believes that a symbiosis network is to improve the economic and environmental efficiency of firms, which is mainly reflected in exchange of by-products, wastes and energies and sharing of resources, technologies and information ^[8].

According to existing studies, in combination with the characteristics of KIBS firms and the firm symbiosis network, the symbiosis network of KIBS firms can be defined as: Through the symbiosis network, KIBS firms can collect, analyze, create and disseminate knowledge, materials and information through integration, process and application internal and external resources, conduct knowledge exchange, information sharing, material circulation and energy conversion in the symbiotic interfaces through the establishment of cooperative symbiotic relationship with symbiotic units, such as the government, other KIBS firms or heterogeneous firms, colleges and universities and scientific research institution, based on the symbiotic environment, and reduce the service innovation cost while not reducing the advantage of service innovation. It has the characteristics of systematicness, openness and dynamic.

Composition of symbiosis network of KIBS firms

In the era of knowledge economy and informatization, for improving service innovation performance, KIBS firms must be able to adapt to the external environment quickly. Therefore, in this study, by taking KIBS firms as the study object, a symbiosis network of KIBS firms is established to create, transfer and exchange knowledge, information and energies, so as to improve KIBS firms' service innovation performance. A symbiosis network is consisted of symbiotic unit, symbiotic relationship, symbiotic environment, and symbiotic interface ^[9].

Symbiotic unit of KIBS firms

The KIBS firms' symbiotic units are the basic units that constitute a symbiosis network and are also the basic units for energy generation and exchange. Symbiotic units in the symbiosis network of KIBS firms mainly include peer firms or heterogeneous firms, scientific research institutions, colleges and universities and governments that participate in service innovation cooperation with KIBS firms. The degree of symbiosis and the degree of association of KIBS firms are important indicators for measuring their degree of service innovation symbiosis ^[10]. The degree of symbiosis emphasizes the degree of mutual influence among symbiotic units. The degree of association emphasizes the degree of closeness between symbiotic units. In service innovation cooperation, improving the "degree of symbiosis" and "degree of association" can promote the sustainable and stable development of cooperation and is conducive to improving the stability of the symbiosis network.

Symbiotic relationship of KIBS firms

The symbiotic relationship of KIBS firms refers to the cooperation relationship between KIBS firms and other symbiotic units, which reflects the way and strength of interaction between symbiotic units, and the exchange of materials, energy and information. From the way of acts, the symbiotic relationship can be divided into: Parasitism, commensalism and mutualism; From the way of organization, the symbiotic relationship can be divided into: Point symbiosis, intermittent symbiosis, continuous symbiosis and integrated symbiosis [11]. The essence of the symbiotic relationship (as shown in Figure 1) established by KIBS firms with other symbiotic units for supply and demand cooperation, technical correlation and business chain is to generate, deliver and exchange knowledge flow, material flow, information flow, energy flow and capital flow between symbiotic units. The symbiotic relationship is a kind of cooperative competition relationship, which is conducive to reducing transaction costs, optimizing resource allocation, reducing risks in the process of knowledge learning, information sharing and energy exchange, and is beneficial to the win-win cooperation of symbiotic units.

Figure 1 The symbiotic relationship of KIBS firms' service innovation

Symbiotic environment of KIBS firms

The symbiotic environment of KIBS firms is the basis for symbiotic units carrying out innovation in the symbiosis network. For the service innovation symbiont of KIBS firms, the function of the symbiotic environment may be positive, neutral and reverse. The reaction of service innovation symbiont of KIBS firms on the symbiotic environment may also be positive, neutral and reverse [12]. The symbiotic environment can affect the transfer speed and efficiency of energy and materials between symbiotic units, mainly including policy environment, market environment, governance environment and information environment.

In the new environment of service innovation and cooperation, the key is the two-way encouragement between KIBS firms engaging in service innovation and cooperation and the symbiotic environment in which they are. To achieve two-way encouragement, symbiosis mechanisms, such as incentive mechanism, constraint mechanism and energy sharing and compensation mechanism, shall be established to guarantee the continuous operation of service innovation and cooperation. For this reason, it not only needs to enhance the enthusiasm of scientific research institutions, local governments and other service innovation subjects in propelling service innovation and cooperation, but also standardizes the transfer of interests among all parties under the premise of equality, mutual benefit and cooperation, to achieve the reasonable distribution of the overall interests among KIBS firms [13].

Symbiotic interface of KIBS firms

KIBS firms' symbiotic interfaces refer to the carrier for the exchange of knowledge, materials, energy and information between symbiotic units, and are the aggregation of ways and mechanisms for the cooperation between KIBS firms and other symbiotic units. It is of significant importance for the formation of the symbiotic relationship and the balance of the symbiosis network. KIBS firms' symbiotic interfaces can be divided into tangible interfaces and intangible interfaces, mainly including the categories and types of service products, the exchange of knowledge and information and social

relationship. KIBS firms' symbiotic interfaces can also be divided into internal interfaces and external interfaces. Among them, internal interfaces refer to the contact mechanism or symbiotic medium between business modules based on service products, including the types, specifications and technical standards of service products provided by each firm. External interfaces refer to the contact mechanism or symbiotic medium between firms based on the business modules, including policies and regulations, market environment, information exchange.^[14] The stability of symbiotic interfaces can be measured from three aspects: Whether they have multiple symbiotic media, whether they have multiplicity and whether they have a perfect operation mechanism ^[15].

The impact of the symbiosis network of KIBS firms on the service innovation capability

The service innovation of KIBS firms may be affected by external organizations, such as peer firms or heterogeneous firms, customers, scientific research institutions and government departments. KIBS firms and these external organizations form the service symbiosis network of KIBS firms together ^[16]. Through the symbiosis network, KIBS firms can obtain important knowledge, technologies and other innovation resources that they do not have, which is conducive to improving their service innovation capability, quality of service innovation activities, and the quality of service innovation products and service contents, and to better meet customers' demands, so as to ultimately improve service innovation performance. The impact of the symbiosis network of KIBS firms on service innovation capability (as shown in Figure 2) mainly includes following three aspects.

Figure 2 The model of impact of the symbiosis network of KIBS firms on service innovation performance

(1) Be conducive to stimulating the service innovation vitality of KIBS firms. Due to the input of human resources, materials and funds for the service innovation of KIBS firms, service innovation together with other symbiotic units is conducive to reducing the risks and costs of service innovation, even increasing the revenue. Therefore, symbiotic units have stronger service innovation vitality in the symbiosis network of KIBS firms.

(2) Be conducive to promoting the service innovation activity of KIBS firms. On account of that service innovation is a complicated process requiring large investment and long term, it is difficult for KIBS firms carrying out service innovation activities with their internal resources. At this time, it is necessary for firms to effectively integrate various internal and external service innovation resources that are closely related to the service innovation activities of firms and that have direct effect on the service innovation activities of firms through the symbiosis network, so as to ensure the normal implementation of service innovation activities and improve the service innovation performance.

(3) Be conducive to promoting the output of service innovation achievements of KIBS firms. The output of service innovation achievements of KIBS firms not only includes the intellectual property rights or technological advantages directly generated by service innovation activities, but also includes the revenue from the industrialization of new intellectual property rights or technological advantages. The core and purpose of KIBS firms' service innovation is to own independent intellectual property rights or technological advantages and gain service innovation revenue through service innovation activities.

Typical service innovation patterns of the symbiosis network of KIBS firms

When carrying out service innovation activities, KIBS firms not only should fully utilize internal resources, but also should obtain external effective innovation resources by establishing symbiotic relationships with other symbiotic units in the symbiosis network. Therefore, in this study, according to the above sorting and summary of literatures related to the service innovation of KIBS firms, in combination with the concept of the symbiosis network of KIBS firms in last section, the innovation

process of the symbiosis network of KIBS firms is divided into inbound innovation, open innovation and ecological innovation, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 The model of the symbiosis network of KIBS firms on service innovation process

Inbound service innovation in the symbiosis network

The first innovation stage of the symbiosis network of KIBS firms is inbound service innovation. In the process, each symbiotic unit will carry out service innovation activities based on the reorganization of existing resources, obtain innovation resources through cooperation with other symbiotic units in the symbiosis network, and then carry out service innovation activities or collaborative innovation with other symbiotic units according to customer demands. In the current market environment, the service innovation capability of each symbiotic unit is mainly reflected in the novelty, price advantage, high cost performance and delivery speed of service products.

Open service innovation in the symbiosis network

The second innovation stage of the symbiosis network of KIBS firms is open service innovation. In the process, the symbiosis network will break through the limitation of internal innovation resources and pay attention to opening up. It will make effort to obtain more innovation resources through the scale and density expansion of the network, and fully explore the existing demands and potential demands of customers, to strive to transform customers into members of the symbiosis network and guide customers to participate in service innovation.

Ecological service innovation in the symbiosis network

The third innovation stage of the symbiosis network of KIBS firms is ecological service innovation. In the process, the symbiosis network can be regarded as a dynamic innovation ecosystem with the increase of scale and enhancement of heterogeneity and openness. The cooperative innovation activities carried out in the symbiosis network pay more attention to the integration of internal and external resources, self-organization and collaboration, coupling and symbiosis, as well as the participation of customers.

Conclusion

In this paper, it attempts to analyze the operational mechanism of the symbiosis network of KIBS firms. Aiming at the characteristics of KIBS firms, it defines the concept of the symbiosis network of KIBS firms, deeply analyzes the composition, characteristics, and innovation process of the symbiosis network of KIBS firms, and on this basis, studies the impact of the symbiosis network of KIBS firms on service innovation capability. On this basis, it explores three basic patterns of service innovation of the symbiosis network of KIBS firms, including inbound service innovation, open service innovation and ecological service innovation.

Therefore, KIBS firms should pay attention to the symbiotic relationship with other firms in the industry or with different heterogeneous firms, and make effort to carry out multi-cooperation through internal learning and training or exchange and learn from other dominant enterprises, to improve their service innovation capability. The service innovation process of KIBS firms is long and complicated. The service innovation of KIBS firms may be affected by external organizations, such as

peer firms or heterogeneous firms, customers, scientific research institutions and government departments. KIBS firms and these external organizations form the service innovation symbiosis network of KIBS firms together. The innovation performance of the symbiosis network may be affected by external and internal environments. In the future, studies on the influencing factors of the service innovation performance of the symbiosis network of KIBS firms and the evaluation of service innovation performance will be further expanded.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This paper was supported by the key project of Beijing Education Commission's Social Science Program-"Research on Evolution Path and Innovation Performance Evaluation of Beijing KIBS Innovation Ecosystem-from the Perspective of Sustainable Development" (Project No. SZ201911232029) from Beijing Information Science and Technology University.

References

- Cai Haizhong. An Empirical Research on Influences of Organization Modularity on Service Innovation Performance in Knowledge Intensive Business Service Firms [D]. Hunan University, 2017.
- Strambach S. Innovation processes and the role of knowledge-intensive business services [A].Koschatzky K, Kulicke M, Zenker A. Innovation Networks Concepts and Challenges in the European Perspective[C].Physica, Heidelberg,1998:53 -68.
- Tether B S,Hipp C,Miles I.Standardisation and particularisation in services: Evidence from Germany[J]. *Research Policy*, 2001,30:1115-1138.
- Freeman C. Networks of innovators:a synthesis of research issues[J].*Research Policy*,1991,20(5):499-514.
- Lambert A J D, Boons F A. Eco-industrial parks : stimulating sustainable development in mixed industrial parks. *Technovation*, 2002,22(8):471-484.
- MIRATAM, EMTAIRAH T. Industrial symbiosis networks and the contribution to environmental innovation: the case of the landskrona industrial symbiosis programme[J]. *Journal of Cleaner Production*,2005(13):993-1002.
- Yuan Zengwei, Bi Jun. Evolution Mechanism of Eco-industrial Symbiosis Network and Its Analytical Framework [J]. *Acta Ecologica Sinica*, 2007(08): 3182-3188.
- Du Pu. Study on the Material Flow Stability of By-products in the Industrial Symbiosis Network [D]. Tianjin University, 2009.
- Liu Lina. Study on Symbiosis Operation between Large Scale Sports Events and Media [J]. *Journal of Liaoning Normal University (Natural Science Edition)*, 2019,42(03):424-432.
- Zhang Qinghui, Li Min. Study on the Symbiosis Model of Collaborative Innovation of Enterprises based on the Life Cycle Theory [J]. *China Management Informationization*, 2014,17(04):106-107.
- Si Shangqi, Cao Zhenquan, Feng Feng. Research on the Cooperation Mechanism of Institutions and Enterprises - A Symbiotic Theory and Analytical Framework [J]. *Science of Science and Management of S.&T.*, 2009,6:15.19.
- Wang Zhaohua, Wu Chunyou. Study on Symbiosis Mechanism of Enterprises in Ecological Industrial Area Base on Exchange Cost Theory. *Science of Science and Management of S.&T.*, 2002.8:9-13.
- Xu Bin. Study of Technical Innovation Management of Small-medium Scientific and Technical Enterprise Based on Symbiosis Theory [J]. *Soft Science*, 2010,24 (11):27-31.
- hi Shuaishuai. Study on the Operational Performance Evaluation of E-commerce Industrial Park Based on Industrial Symbiosis [D]. Fuzhou University, 2017.
- Tang Weining. Study on the Development Mechanism and Policy Support of Logistics Industry Cluster Based on the Symbiosis Theory [J]. *Enterprise Economy*, 2009 (05):152-155.
- Mustak M. Service Innovation in Networks:A Systematic Review and Implications for Business to Business Service Innovation Research.*Journal of Business&Industrial Marketing*, 2014, 29(2):151-163.